

MANAGEMENT OF FLY ASH FROM BIOMASS COMBUSTION

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Summary. The efficient management of biomass fly ash is a key factor for the circular economy. Fly ash is produced in large quantities during biomass combustion and may be utilized for various applications, for both environmental and financial benefits. The main limitation of biomass fly ash utilization is its unrecognized potential caused by a lack of consistent law regulations. In this paper, possible paths of biomass fly ash management are discussed. The compositions of 4 fly ashes derived from biomass combustion in Polish units are presented, together with 2 examples of phosphorous-rich ashes. The five most promising ways of management are elaborated: concrete and cement production, phosphorous recovery and fertilizers, composites, ceramics, and sorbents. The latest state-of-the-art research regarding each path is briefly reviewed and current law regulations are introduced. Limitations for the safe management of biomass ash are also discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the Polish Regulation of the Ministry of Climate of January 2, 2020 on the waste catalog, waste from the thermal conversion of fuels belongs to group 10: "Waste from thermal processes". Of particular interest is waste classified in group 10 01 "Waste from power plants and other fuel combustion plants". Within this group, combustion waste is further classified depending on its type (e.g. fly ash, slag, flue gas desulfurization by-products, etc.), fuel of origin (e.g. coal, wood), and the process of origin (e.g. combustion, co-combustion, flue gas treatment). The classification also takes into account hazardous waste. Fly ashes originating from pure biomass combustion are described as group no 10 03: Fly ashes from peat and untreated wood.

Therefore, fly ashes from the combustion of both coal and biomass are legally classified as waste. Nevertheless, when it comes to coal fly ash, its use in the industry has been allowed to a certain extent. Coal fly ash has been used for concrete production according to the standards described in this paper in section 3.1.

The utilization of biomass ash is a relatively new topic and is poorly regulated by law. Some individual legal acts take it into account, nevertheless, there is a lack of complex regulation in this field. A current Regulation of the Minister of Climate and Environment of October 27, 2022, has been published, specifying the detailed conditions for the loss of waste status for waste generated in the processes of energy combustion of fuels. The regulation specifies, that fly ash is no longer a waste if it fulfills the criteria defined in specific standards. However, most of these standards have been developed for coal fly ash, and therefore biomass ash may not fulfill them.

As presented in this paper, fly ash from biomass combustion can be a key material for the circular economy, providing both environmental and financial benefits.

2. BIOMASS ASH COMPOSITION

According to the data presented in the "Map of biomass-fired installations" [11], in Poland, there are over 40 heat plants and heat and power plants utilizing biomass. This is reflected in the amount of biomass fly ash being produced every year. However, the composition of various biomass ashes may differ significantly depending on the fuel type and furnace type. Biomass composition is much more diverse than coal, even within one plant species, as it depends even on factors such as soil, growing conditions, and weather.

To display the fly ash composition, usually, the concentrations of the following main elements are determined in oxide form: sulfur as SO_3 , potassium as K_2O , silicon as SiO_2 , iron as Fe_2O_3 , aluminum as Al_2O_3 , manganese as Mn_3O_4 , titanium as TiO_2 , calcium as CaO , magnesium as MgO , phosphorus as P_2O_5 , sodium as Na_2O , barium as BaO , and strontium as SrO . This is the most popular way of presenting ash composition, nevertheless, it assumes that the elements got completely oxidized during the combustion process. This assumption may, however, not reflect reality, for example, alkali metals (K, Na) may be present in ash in the form of chlorides, sulfates, and carbonates as well. Despite this assumption, this method is widely used by researchers and is presented in most papers. The loss of ignition (LOI) is also determined, as it characterizes the combustion process.

The compositions of 4 fly ashes derived from biomass combustion in Polish units are presented in table 1. The ashes can be described as:

A1 – fly ash from wood biomass combustion in a circulating fluidized boiler (CFB). A2 – fly ash from biomass combustion in a CFB

A3 – fly ash from biomass combustion in a CFB

A4 – fly ash from biomass combustion in a bubbling fluidized boiler (BFB).

Table 1.
Composition of biomass-derived fly ashes collected from Polish units (n.d. – no data available)

Ash composition, wt%	A1	A2	A3 [24]	A4 [24]
SiO ₂	36.30	54.21	32.40	34.10
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.20	2.58	2.53	2.90
Al ₂ O ₃	5.70	9.05	6.21	4.56
Mn ₃ O ₄	0.55	0.43	n.d.	n.d.
TiO ₂	0.45	0.37	n.d.	n.d.
CaO	16.20	14.61	8.62	21.23
MgO	4.50	3.03	3.42	5.64
SO ₃	8.90	3.94	3.10	10.00
P ₂ O ₅	2.60	2.06	n.d.	n.d.
Na ₂ O	1.16	0.67	0.50	0.60
K ₂ O	13.20	8.93	3.70	13.70
BaO	<0.1	0.08	n.d.	n.d.
SrO	0.05	0.05	n.d.	n.d.
Loss of ignition (LOI)	n.d.	6.57	4.30	6.70

As displayed in table 1, the ashes are characterized by predominant contents of silicon (32.40-54.21% of SiO₂), remarkable contents of calcium (21.23-8.62% of CaO), potassium (3.70-13.70 of K₂O), sulfur (3.10-10.00% SO₃), aluminum (4.56-9.05)% of Al₂O₃) and magnesium (3.03-5.64% of MgO).

The analyses of some biomass fly ashes revealed the presence of numerous fly ash microspheres (FAM). A scanning electron microscope (SEM) picture of a microsphere in ash A1 is presented in Figure 1. FAM possess a spherical morphology and a level of fineness that is much smaller than ordinary fly ash particles. They are lightweight and inert, made mostly of silica and alumina, and filled with air or inert gas. Fly ashes rich in microspheres are desired materials for various applications. FAM can be also separated from ash for further processing and use. Microspheres have been proven to positively influence concrete properties, as well as may be utilized in composites based on glass or polymers. In recent years, microspheres have been employed for additive manufacturing as well, in the form of silicone-shell microballoons or thermally expandable microspheres.

Fig. 1. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of a microsphere in A1 biomass fly ash

3. MANAGEMENT PATHS

In this paper, the following paths of biomass ash management are taken into account: concrete and cement production, phosphorous recovery and fertilizers, composites, ceramics, and sorbents. These paths are claimed to be the most promising in terms of expected benefits, both environmental and economic.

3.1. Concrete and cement

One of the most popular ways of utilizing fly ash, particularly resulting from the combustion of hard coal, is to use it for concrete production. Detailed parameters and conditions allowing the use of ash in cement production are specified in standard PN EN 197-1:2012: “Cement - Part 1: Composition, specifications and conformity criteria for common cements”, and allowing the use of ash in concrete production in standards EN 450-1:2012: “Fly ash for concrete definition, specifications and conformity criteria” and PN-EN 206+A2:2021-08: “Concrete - requirements, properties, production and compliance”. The first standard regards the use of fly ash in concrete, while the second specifies general guidelines for concrete production applicable in Polish and European law.

When it comes to the use of biomass ash in concrete production, it was recently mentioned by the current version of the standard EN 450, which allows the use of ash from biomass co-combustion with coal.

The standards listed above set numerous conditions for ash, including particle size, maximum loss of ignition, specific chemical composition, specific physical properties, volume constancy, declared grain density, declared setting onset, limited release of hazardous substances, and natural radioactivity.

Taking into account the decreasing interest in coal-fired plants and growing interest in the circular economy, lawmakers should deal with biomass ash as soon as possible. Despite this law gap, in recent years, there has been an increasing number of research dealing with the addition of pure biomass ash to concrete and cement. Reviewing some of the research, the conclusions are mixed. Various factors, including the type of biomass ash, particle size distribution, and mass fraction of ash in the mix influence the physical properties of concrete. Studies have shown that the addition of biomass ash to concrete can improve its workability and physical properties, but may also result in an extended setting time and an increased water demand [14]. The work by Odeymi et al. [13] showed that the addition of bamboo ash improves the mechanical properties of concrete and extends its durability. Similarly, the results by Nagrockienė and Daugėl [12] showed that biomass ash added to concrete positively affects the mechanical properties, and the suggested optimal mass share of ash in the mixture is up to 15%. On the other hand, the authors of [15] examined the addition of rice husk ash and obtained a noticeable decrease in the workability of concrete with an increase in the mass fraction of ash. However, concrete containing 10–15% husk ash has been found to meet the requirements for use in construction.

The long-term studies involving the durability and sustainability of concrete with biomass ash are not available yet. There are currently no standards for the processing of biomass ash for concrete production, which makes many research incomparable to each other. To increase the use of biomass ash in civil engineering, an effort should be made to standardize it and set proper regulations.

3.2. Phosphorous recovery and fertilizers

Phosphate rock is a non-renewable natural resource commonly used as a raw material for P-fertilizer production. Unluckily, phosphate rock reserves that are easily accessible and low in impurities are now about to deplete. Therefore several technologies are emerging for phosphorus recovery from waste materials, such as fly ash. Some types of ash are above-average rich in phosphorus, such as sewage sludge ash and animal litter ash, whose compositions are presented in table 2. The ashes presented in the table were produced by laboratory incineration of chicken litter and sewage sludge in a heated chamber in a temperature zone of 550 °C.

Table 2.

Composition of ashes with high phosphorous contents

Ash composition, wt%	Chicken litter	Sewage sludge
SO ₃	0,82	4,2
K ₂ O	16,54	1,87
SiO ₂	13,26	30,2
Fe ₂ O ₃	1,84	5,8
Al ₂ O ₃	2,81	7,36
Mn ₃ O ₄	1,86	0,09
TiO ₂	0,43	0,58
CaO	26,61	29,49
MgO	5,72	2,83
P ₂ O ₅	23,74	14,72
Na ₂ O	5,74	2,07
BaO	0,14	0,03
SrO	0,31	0,06

The combustion of animal litter is gaining interest in recent years, as it is a cheap and widely available type of biomass. According to Polish law, animal litter is classified as biomass and according to EU Commission Regulation no 142/2011 of 25 February 2011 poultry litter can be used in combustion units, and according to Regulation no. 2017/1262 of 12 July 2017 other animal litter can also be utilized: “Manure of farmed animals may present a sustainable source of fuel for combustion (...). Manure of farmed animals of species other than poultry may now also be used as a fuel in combustion plants with a total rated thermal input not exceeding 50 MW, under the same conditions as set out for the combustion of poultry manure, including the emission limits and monitoring requirements.” Animal litter therefore may be a promising feedstock for both energy and phosphorous recovery.

Biomass ash shows good bioavailability during field and pot tests and can be directly applied into a field as a phosphorous source, applied in the form of hydrated ash, or phosphorous can be recovered by extraction or elution. Fiameni et al. [5] proposed a strategy for phosphorous and silica recovery from poultry litter ash. The proposed method aims to maximize the extraction using hydrochloric acid and minimize the possible contamination by leachable heavy metals, such as zinc.

The recirculation of biomass ash into the soil is often claimed to be the most sustainable disposal method according to the circular economy idea. Therefore, the EU allowed the marketing of fertilizer products of various origins, including ash from biomass combustion, within the scope of solid inorganic macronutrient fertilizers. This issue has been regulated by the recent EU Fertilising Products

Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, which was approved on 5 June 2019. When the requirements of the Regulation are fulfilled, the ash is no longer considered waste, and it can be used as a component for fertilizing products. The products containing or consisting of such recovered ash are allowed to access the European market.

3.3. Composites

A relatively new and innovative path for ash management is its use as a filler in the production and processing of polymers, such as polypropylene (PP), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyethylene (PE), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

Polymer-based products with ash are often characterized by better mechanical properties and abrasion resistance as well as lower flammability. Kuźnia et al. [10] produced rigid polyurethane foams reinforced with 5 and 10% of fly ash. The ash addition improved the mechanical properties and thermal stability of the resulting composite. Moreover, the use of ash in composites increased the friability of the composite. In other words, the composites do not crack and are less brittle. As confirmed by the research of Gnatowski et al. [7], the addition of biomass ash to polyamide influenced the thermal and mechanical properties of the material and the compatibility of the polymer matrix and the filler. It was observed that the addition of 5% ash had a greater strengthening effect than the addition of a larger dose. Another study [16] determined the effect of the addition of biomass ash on the cracking and thermal characteristics of polypropylene composites. Various composites based on polypropylene, olefin block copolymer, and biomass ash in different ratios were tested. The composites were characterized by higher strength than pure polypropylene.

Most polymers are characterized by low melting points and, consequently, low thermal stability. The addition of ash, which is non-flammable and characterized by a relatively high melting point, may visibly increase these parameters. The authors of [6] examined the addition of rice husk ash, characterized by a high silicon content, to low-density polyethylene (LDPE) to reduce flammability and increase the resistance to thermal degradation. The results of thermal analysis (DSC) showed an increase in the melting point of the ash-containing composite. This indicated the possible use of ash composites as materials with favorable thermal properties, suitable for industrial applications such as pipes and protective coatings that require increased thermal resistance, while simultaneously reducing production costs.

The authors of [23] assessed the usability of composites based on epoxy resin with the addition of biomass ash for sound absorption. The research shows that composites with ash have a better sound absorption capacity compared to the reference sample.

The work [18] presents the production and characteristics of lightweight synthetic aggregates with the addition of biomass ash. The aggregates are intended for applications in geotechnical engineering (lightweight embankments, re-profiling of slopes, backfill against foundations, retaining walls, drain trenches in slopes, pavements systems, as well as vibration isolation, etc.). The aggregates were produced by thermal extrusion of HDPE with fly ash in a weight ratio of 1:1. After analyzing the produced aggregate and determining its physicochemical and mechanical properties, it was considered promising in terms of potential use in geotechnical engineering.

3.4. Ceramics

Biomass ashes can be used instead of raw materials for the production of ceramic, glass, and glazed products. In the work by Conte et al. [4] biomass ash was used to produce porcelain stoneware elements. The ash works as a flux, so it was used to partially replace popularly used feldspar. The presence of ash improved the thermal stability of a product while maintaining other parameters comparable to those of the reference sample.

The research [2] determined the positive effect of the addition of fly ash, especially the microspheres, on the mechanical strength and weight reduction of roof tiles. The authors of [22] present the possibility of using ash from waste combustion in the brick production process. Research suggests that the ash addition of 4% improves the mechanical properties of bricks, especially their compressive strength. The aesthetic aspect can be also improved by ash addition: The addition of wood ash in ceramic products acts as a natural pigment that brightens its color [9].

Fly ash may be used as a component of refractory materials due to its non-flammability, and the presence of high-melting compounds such as mullite or calcsylite, whose melting points are above 1500 °C. Fly ash can be used in other ceramic products, such as ceramic membranes, construction blocks, and insulators.

3.5. Sorbents

Sorption is a method of removing undesirable elements from liquid and gaseous media, such as the removal of heavy metals from sewage, primarily

those from the mining and metallurgical industries. Removal of heavy metals from sewage water is carried out using various adsorbents, and the most effective are activated carbons. However, due to the high cost of their use, cheaper materials, so-called low-cost adsorbents, are being sought. One of the frequently considered low-cost adsorbents is fly ash. In recent years, many studies have been published on this issue, however, usually, coal ash is regarded and only a few studies deal with biomass ash. In the work by Reczek et al. [19] the possibility of using fly ash from biomass combustion and co-combustion of biomass is assessed for the sorption of lead(II) ions from aqueous solutions, and positive results were achieved. In the work [17], the sorption of dyes from aqueous solution was investigated using coal fly ash, HCl-activated coal ash, and biomass fly ash. Biomass ash showed the highest adsorption capacity for both tested dyes compared to the other two ashes. Similarly, in [1], sorbents originating from biomass ash showed the efficiency of removing methylene blue from wastewater of up to 80%.

Fly ash can also adsorb elemental mercury (Hg^0), as proven in the works of Charpentreau et al. [3]. The use of biomass ash in this direction seems extremely promising due to its favorable composition, high porosity, and developed specific surface.

Another way is CO_2 sorption. In a study [25], mesoporous silica was extracted from biomass ash and tested for CO_2 adsorption. The prepared material was characterized by a large specific surface area of $495 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and showed excellent CO_2 adsorption properties as well as very good regeneration ability and adsorption selectivity. The work [8] examined the CO_2 sorption capacity of activated carbon derived from biomass ash. The activation process increased the specific surface area to $248 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and doubled the CO_2 absorption capacity compared to non-activated carbon, making the tested adsorbent competitive with commercial products intended for low-temperature carbon dioxide capture.

4. LIMITATIONS

When considering potential fly ash application the possible limitations cannot be ignored. The main issue is the content of metals and metalloids, such as zinc (Zn), mercury (Hg), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), and cadmium (Cd). These elements may be characterized by high mobility and leachability, and therefore migrate from the ash to the environment. Their content in fly ash may become a serious issue, as complex flue gas treatment systems are becoming a must due to increasingly stringent emission standards. Therefore, unwanted elements

such as heavy metals are fixed in fly ash, instead of being emitted with flue gas. The contents of Zn, Hg, Cu, Ni, Pb, Cr, and Cd contents in selected biomass ashes are presented in table 3.

Table 3.
Metals contents in biomass ashes, mg/kg
(n.d. – no data available)

	Birch [19]	Spruce [19]	Chicken litter	Sewage sludge [21]
Zn	3910–43.500	2630–7910	846–3400	2535
Hg	0.2–1.7	0.1–1.2	<0.05	n.d.
Cu	138–650	294–860	109–612	821
Ni	18–156	1.4–80	16.0–99.0	64
Pb	37–13.700	8–1290	2.37–49.30	248
Cr	147–508	183–342	24–73	121
Cd	26–203	184–4	<2.93	7

The EU Fertilising Products Regulation 2019/1009, mentioned in this paper in section 3.2., sets the limits for heavy metals and metalloids concentration in inorganic macronutrient fertilizers. The maximum concentrations are: Zn 1500 mg/kg, Hg 1 mg/kg, Cu 600 mg/kg, Ni 100 mg/kg, Pb 120 mg/kg, Cr 2 mg/kg, Cd 3 and 60 mg/kg.

Ash with particularly high concentrations of heavy metals may need immobilization, which is a process of chemical transformation in such a way that soluble compounds, in this case, metals, cannot be eluted. Such ash may be utilized as components in geopolymers or glass, both of which show very good ability for the immobilization of heavy metals.

5. SUMMARY

Fly ash from the combustion of biomass may be a valuable feedstock for utilization in various industries. It can partially replace raw materials, leading to environmental and economic benefits. Most biomass ash types contain mostly silicon (SiO_2) or are rich in calcium (CaO) while others are above average rich in phosphorus. The possible application paths may be diverse, such as concrete and cement production, phosphorous recovery and fertilizers, composites, ceramics, and sorbents. However, the biggest limitation of the use of biomass ash is a lack of consistent law regulations, with so-called “fertilizing regulation” being the only detailed act that deals with biomass ash. Taking into account the decreasing interest in coal-fired plants and growing interest in the circular economy, the lawmakers

should work on the issue of biomass utilization ash as soon as possible.

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WYKORZYSTANIE POPIOŁÓW ZE SPALANIA BIOMASY

Słowa kluczowe: biomasa, popiół, popiół lotny, gospodarka odpadami

Streszczenie. Zagospodarowanie popiołów lotnych z biomasy jest ważnym elementem gospodarki o obiegu zamkniętym (GOZ). Popiół lotny powstaje w znacznych ilościach podczas spalania biomasy, a jego odpowiednie zagospodarowanie może przynieść zarówno korzyści dla środowiska, jak i oszczędności finansowe. Głównym ograniczeniem wykorzystania popiołów lotnych z biomasy jest brak odpowiednich uregulowań prawnych, co powoduje również słabe rozpoznanie możliwości użycia popiołów. W artykule przedstawiono składy 4 popiołów lotnych pochodzących ze spalania biomasy w polskich obiektach energetyki zawodowej oraz 2 przykłady popiołów szczególnie bogatych w fosfor. Omówiono pięć najbardziej obiecujących sposobów wykorzystania: produkcja betonów i cementu, odzysk fosforu i zastosowanie jako nawozy, składnik kompozytów, materiały ceramiczne oraz sorbenty. Przedstawiono aktualne regulacje prawne oraz dokonano krótkiego przeglądu najnowszych badań dotyczących poszczególnych ścieżek. Omówiono także ograniczenia w zakresie bezpiecznego zagospodarowania popiołów z biomasy.

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